

Fabrication and characterization of pervaporative nanocomposite membrane for removal of benzene from model pyrolysis gasoline

Monalisha Samanta, Sayan Roychowdhury and Debarati Mitra*

Department of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail: samanta.monalisha37@gmail.com, roychowdhury.romeo@gmail.com, debarati_che@yahoo.com

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Removal of benzene from pyrolysis gasoline is important to meet automobile emission specifications. EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) – MSAT (Mobile Source Air Toxic) requires refiners to meet an annual average benzene content of 0.62% by volume in gasoline. According to BS VI the maximum allowable concentration of benzene in pyrolysis gasoline should be less than 1% volume (max). A polyimide-polyaniline nanocomposite membrane was fabricated by solution casting a mixture of polyamic acid, *N,N*-dimethylacetamide and polyaniline. The prepared membrane was characterized by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and swelling study. This membrane was utilized for the separation of benzene from model pyrolysis gasoline via pervaporation. About 80% benzene removal was achieved. Hence it can be concluded that the novel nanocomposite membrane fabricated using a simple and relatively inexpensive method has good potentiality for pervaporative removal of benzene from the chosen system.

Keywords: Nanocomposite membrane, benzene, model pyrolysis gasoline, pervaporation.

Introduction

Pyrolysis gasoline (Py gas) is an important fractionating cut from the petrochemicals industry as well as refinery. Py gas is a light yellowish flammable, low boiling (40–90°C) liquid. It is a by-product of naphtha cracking during production of olefins. Py gas, a naphtha range (C₆–C₁₂) product, is usually a mixture of aromatics (40–80%), olefins and paraffins. It is generally used as a gasoline blending component due to its high octane number. However, Py gas is rich in benzene which is a confirmed carcinogen^{1,2} declared by IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer) and EPA.

When Py gas rich in benzene (benzene ≥ 40%) is blended into gasoline to improve its octane number release of benzene into the atmosphere may be caused due to incomplete combustion of such gasoline in vehicles resulting in environmental pollution. Thus, we can infer that there is an urgent need of separating benzene from Py gas prior to blending with gasoline. Conventional processes of benzene removal from Py gas are – (1) Catalytic hydrogenation with Ni or Pd catalyst³; (2) Extractive distillation using *N*-methyl pyrrolidone as solvent⁴. But both the processes are complex and energy intensive.

Recently, an increasing trend in membrane technology has been the focus of separation processes in chemical industry. The main reason for appreciating membrane technology over classical methods of separation and purification is that the conventional processes are energy consuming and expensive. In such case, pervaporation (PV), a unique membrane technique (combination of membrane permeation and downstream evaporation) can be applied for separating benzene from Py gas using a suitable polymeric membrane⁵.

Vanherck *et al.* reviewed that polyimide is an excellent polymer to prepare membranes because of its outstanding heat resistance, good mechanical strength and chemical resistance to many solvents⁶. Polotskaya, Pulyalina and co researchers prepared nanocomposite membrane of polyimide-polyaniline by mixing poly[[4,4'-bis(4''-*N*-phenoxy)diphenylsulfone]imide-1,3-bis(3,4-dicarboxyphenoxy)benzene] (PI) and polyaniline (PANI) in *N*-methyl pyrrolidone. This membrane was applied for the separation of organic mixtures: methanol/toluene and methanol/cyclohexane. They observed that PI/PANI membrane is a hydrophilic membrane^{7,8}.

In our present work, we have chosen a mixture of ben-

zene, toluene, xylene, n-heptane, 1-octene as a model Py gas and fabricated a unique nanocomposite polyimide based membrane for separation of benzene from this model Py gas using PV. In this case PANI was used as nano material to be incorporated in polyamic acid for preparation of PI/PANI nanocomposite membrane, since, PANI has high electro-conductivity and high resistant towards most organic-organic mixtures^{7,8}. At first, PANI nano particles were produced by using ammonium persulfate and aniline. Laminar nanocomposite membranes had been prepared by casting of PI/PANI mixture on a glass plate. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was done to analyze the size of PANI and also to analyze the surface morphology of PI/PANI membrane. PI/PANI membrane was also characterized using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and swelling ratio. The percentage of removal of benzene from model Py gas was evaluated.

Materials and methods:

Materials:

Benzene, toluene, xylene, n-heptane, 1-octene and dioctyl sebacate (all are GC grade) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, USA to prepare model Py gas. Polyamic acid, dissolved in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (DMAc) was supplied by ABR Organics, Hyderabad. Aniline, ammonium persulfate (APS) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) were purchased from Merck Life Science Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai for producing PANI.

PANI preparation:

4.5–4.8 g aniline was dissolved in 50 ml 1(*M*) HCl acid. 11.8–12 g APS was dissolved in 50 ml distilled water. These solutions were mixed and stirred for 24 h at 273 K. A green precipitation of PANI salt was observed^{7,8}. This green PANI salt was washed with ammonium hydroxide to get base PANI i.e. a blue precipitate.

Membrane preparation:

The membrane casting solution was prepared by mixing PI dissolved in solvent DMAc with 0.1 weight % PANI (also dissolved in DMAc) and stirring for 2 h at 298 K. The solution was casted on a glass plate at 308 K and then the film was dried in a vacuum oven at 318 K for 30 min. After solvent evaporation, the film was immersed in toluene for 24 h and in di-octyl sebacate for next 24 h for gelation. Finally the film was imidized in a furnace at 373 K for 1 h, 473 K for 1 h and 573 K for 1 h. The imidized membrane was dipped into metha-

nol for 24 h and lastly dried for PV experiment^{7,9,10}. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of membrane preparation.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of membrane preparation.

Sorption test:

Interaction of feed mixture with membrane components was determined by the gravimetric sorption test. Membrane strips of 0.5 g were immersed into feed mixtures containing benzene as well as feed mixture without benzene at an operating temperature (313 K). Periodically, the strips were removed and blotted with tissue paper to remove excess liquid from surfaces of strips. Then the strips were weighed immediately. The swollen membrane was then dried at 333 K in a vacuum oven to determine the weight of the dry membranes. From the swelling test, the percentage sorption was calculated using the equation⁹,

$$\% \text{ Sorption} = \frac{M_s - M_d}{M_d} \times 100$$

where M_s and M_d are the weights of swollen and dry membranes respectively.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM):

The size of the PANI was analyzed using the Scanning Electron Microscope (ZEISS EVO18, Germany) equipped with Ion Sputter E1010. The surface morphology and cross section of virgin PI/PANI membrane and worked membrane were also analyzed with the same SEM instrument. Before conducting SEM, all the samples were silver coated with sputter coater.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR):

FTIR were used for group analysis of PANI nanoparticles and PI/PANI membrane with the help of 6300 JASCO FTIR spectrometer. The spectrum range was 400–4000 cm^{-1} .

Pervaporation experiments:

The PV operation was performed in a laboratory scale batch set up. The PV instrument consisted of a stainless permeation cell where PI/PANI membrane was placed on a porous metal support, a feed agitator, cold trap for permeate collection through vacuum pump bearing McLeod Gauge to measure the downstream pressure. The effective membrane area for contacting the feed mixture was $37.40 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$. After PV experiment, components (permeate and retentate) were analyzed using Gas Chromatography (GC). Fig. 2 shows that the schematic diagram of the PV set-up. The operating temperature was varied from 298 K to 318 K in 1 mm Hg vacuum pressure.

Table 1. Different feed compositions used for the experiments¹⁰

Vol (%)	F1	F2	F3
Benzene	20	30	40
Toluene	30	20	10
Xylene	10	10	10
1-Octene	30	30	30
n-Heptane	10	10	10

due to swelling by model Py gas after PV experiment. From the cross-section image (Fig. 4) it is seen that the top layer of PI/PANI membrane is a smooth surface, the bottom layer is highly porous due to presence of PANI nanoparticles.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR):

The FTIR (Fig. 5) analysis of PANI, PI membrane and PI/PANI membrane were conducted in the range $400\text{--}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The characteristic peaks of PANI at 1589.15 cm^{-1} and 1498 cm^{-1} are due to the C-C stretching of the quinonoid (Q) and benzenoid (N) rings respectively¹¹. A noticeable peak of PANI for N-H stretching has occurred at 3230 cm^{-1} . The N-Q-N stretching at 1163 cm^{-1} indicates the successful functionalization of PANI. Symmetric stretching at 1720 cm^{-1} for C=O and stretching at 1380 cm^{-1} due to C-N have been observed for the PI membrane¹⁰. For the PI/PANI membrane, clear peaks at 1714 cm^{-1} for C=O stretching, 1372 cm^{-1} for C-N stretching, 3018 cm^{-1} for N-H stretching and 1154 cm^{-1} for N-Q-N stretching are evident.

Sorption analysis:

The sorption analysis gives the interaction between PI/

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of PV set up.

Results and discussion

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM):

The particle size of the PANI is analyzed by used of SEM. From Fig. 3 shows that nano sized PANI particles have been generated. The diameter of the nano PANI is approx. 100 nm.

The surface morphology and cross-section of virgin PI/PANI membrane and worked (after PV experiment) membrane were analyzed by SEM. From SEM images, it is observed that the surface of the virgin PI/PANI membrane is smooth but the surface of worked PI/PANI membrane is rough

Fig. 3. SEM image of PANI.

Fig. 4. (A) SEM image of virgin PI/PANI membrane, (B) Cross section image of virgin PI/PANI membrane, (C) SEM image of worked (after PV experiment) PI/PANI membrane, (D) Cross section image of worked (after PV experiment) PI/PANI membrane.

Fig. 5. FTIR analysis of PANI particles, PI membrane and PI/PANI membrane.

Fig. 6. Percentage of sorption of PI/PANI membrane.

PANI membrane and component of model Py⁷ gas. From the sorption graph, we observe that PI/PANI membrane has less affinity towards benzene. It is evident that an increase in % of sorption occurred in case of feed solutions without benzene and equilibrium sorption was established at 50 h in both the cases (Fig. 6).

Percentage removal of benzene:

From GC data, it is observed that the retentate is benzene rich compared to the permeate. From the Fig. 7, it is evident that the percentage of removal of benzene increases

with increasing temperature and decreasing feed concentration at 1 mm Hg pressure. But after 313 K the removal of benzene has dropped due to excessive evaporation (boiling point of Py gas 313–353 K) of feed mixture. Also we can see (Fig. 7) that the percentage of removal decreases beyond 30 vol% benzene in feed concentration because PI/PANI membrane is hydrophilic in nature⁸. The percentage removal of benzene from model Py gas is 80% at 313 K under 1 mm Hg pressure.

Fig. 7. Percentage of removal of benzene from model Py gas using PI/PANI membrane.

Conclusion

Removal of benzene from Py gas is a challenging work in petroleum industry. We have studied the separation of benzene from model Py gas using a unique nanocomposite membrane through PV technique. PANI and PI/PANI membrane were prepared using simple and inexpensive methods. We have observed that the retentate is benzene rich. The percentage of removal of benzene from model Py gas was about 80% for 30 vol% benzene in feed mixture at 313

K under 1 mm Hg pressure. Hence it can be inferred that, this nanocomposite PI/PANI membrane is suitable for separation of benzene from Py gas.

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